

Parenting style and emotional intelligence as the predictors of academic buoyancy among the senior secondary students

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ABSTRACT

The current research is the study of academic buoyancy in relation to emotional intelligence and parenting styles. Academic buoyancy is a strength in a student's life to deal with the routine problems in classroom study like low grades, negative feedback by teachers, and difficulties in understanding of concepts. For the studying the relationship between the variables, data was collected from the various school of Punjab state. The data of 1,149 students were used for the analysis. The results of the research explained that academic buoyancy and emotional intelligence of the girls was found to be significantly higher than boys. Among the four parenting styles there was also gender difference. Furthermore, on the basis of stream, there was a significant difference in all the variables. In correlation analysis, there was a significant relationship between academic buoyancy and emotional intelligence. Moreover, findings of the research revealed that, both emotional intelligence and parenting styles were found to be significant predictors of academic buoyancy. So, this research is very helpful for the parents, school principals, policymakers, and administrators.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Academic buoyancy is a strength of an individual to efficiently manage academic demands, obstacles, and failures in learning environments while keeping a positive attitude and tenacity in pursuit of their academic objectives. It entails having the ability to recover from challenges, disappointments, and pressures faced when learning. Resilience and academic buoyancy are closely connected, although academic buoyancy focuses on the academic setting especially. The present research attempts to study that how academic buoyancy varies in students in relation to parenting styles and emotional intelligence. Furthermore, this research attempts to compare the academic buoyancy of students of different streams (science, commerce, and arts).

The examination of the literature indicated that academic buoyancy has been the focus of much research in recent years. Motivation was discovered to have an impact on academic buoyancy [1]. Similarly, grit has significant impact on academic buoyancy of students [2]. Self-efficacy has a significant impact on the buoyancy [3], [4]. Several studies have shown that anxiety has a detrimental impact on academic buoyancy [5]. There was also a negative impact of test-anxiety on academic buoyancy [6]. It is also negatively related to psychological risk [7] and school related stress [8]. Moreover, academic buoyancy was found to be related to personal best goal [9] and student's wellbeing [10]. In addition to this, academic buoyancy playing an important role in achievement of the students in their academic life [11], [12]. The

academic buoyancy also influenced by teacher's emotional support [13], engagement of the student in the class room [14]–[16], thinking pattern center [17], emotional intelligence of the pupil [18], adaptability [19], Culture belief of the individual and self-belief [20] and positive youth development [21].

For the past many years, research on parenting has been ongoing. Family is where a child receives his fundamental socialization. It serves as the foundation for socialization since it is here that the child learns social norms, develops worldviews, and learns how to behave in a proper and acceptable manner in public. In any event, the parent-child relationship is the most important relationship and has the most impact on the development of the child. It is abundantly obvious from the research study that parenting style is associated to emotional creativity [22]. Additionally, it impacts the student's academic performance [23]. According to the study's findings, academic socialization and both mastery goals and performance-approach objectives are positively correlated [24]. Academic success is also impacted by a student's parenting style [25]. Additionally, parenting style reduces a child's propensity for prosocial behaviors [26]. Moreover, it aids in addressing children's behavior issues [27]. Parenting practices can enhance a child's mental health [28]. According to a study, a child's happiness is predicted by the parent's parenting style [29]. The student's career self-efficacy is also increased by the parenting style [30] and social skill of the child also effected by the parenting style [31]. Parenting style show a large variation on the basis of gender [32]. Thus, a study of the research showed that parenting practices are crucial to a child's growth. It has been explored using several recent factors. There is still space for more investigation. In order to determine how parenting style affects other variables, such as academic buoyancy, it may be studied as an independent variable.

A person's emotions are influenced by the experiences in their life. Emotions also include our real-world imagination. An organisms moved or stirred-up condition is referred to as emotion. It is a worked-up state of feeling, and the individual himself will only see it in that way. On the other hand, emotions affect the routine activities of an individual.

A thorough examination of the literature indicated a connection between parenting style and emotional intelligence [33]–[35], whereas, is influenced by stress [36]. Moreover, the emotional intelligence is found to be related to well-being [37], personality [38] and self-efficacy [39] of the individual. Additionally, emotional intelligence increases pupils' academic achievement [40]. Emotional intelligence also shows great variation on the basis of gender [41]. As a result, we can state that the variable emotional intelligence has been thoroughly investigated for a very long time. There still exists a need for more investigation. It might be looked at as an independent variable with academic buoyancy.

The fact that current Indian educational system is exceedingly stressful for the pupils led to the necessity to carry out this study. The low educational performance in many areas of India is a result of teachers' absences, incompetent teachers, poor teaching and learning processes, and a lack of teaching resources [42]. Another problem is that students frequently leave the schools in rural areas because of inadequate economic infrastructure. Students have experienced dual pressure from both their families and their schools [43]. Students in contemporary India experience stress and anxiety due to the strain of competitiveness [44]. Depression and anxiety are quite prevalent among Indian students due to academic stress [45]. We must increase students' academic buoyancy in order to combat these issues in India. As a last consideration, this research will be highly beneficial for parents who want to know how to raise their children for better academic success. Moreover, this research is beneficial for school administrators who want to provide a positive learning environment for kids.

From the above discussion, the following hypothesis have been framed; H₀₁: There is no significant difference in academic buoyancy, emotional intelligence and parenting styles on the basis of gender and stream, H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between academic buoyancy, emotional intelligence and parenting styles, and H₀₃: There is no joint contribution emotional intelligence and parenting styles in prediction of academic buoyancy.

2. METHOD

2.1. Research method

The current study was conducted by using a descriptive survey research approach. This specific research approach has been the most widely used and often employed in the social sciences. Descriptive research describes the characteristics of the population or phenomenon being studied. The researcher visited each school and received permission from the administrators to gather the necessary data.

2.2. Population and sample

All the students of senior secondary level in Punjab state schools served as the population for this study. In Punjab state, there are more than 2000 senior secondary schools. 30 schools were chosen at random from these schools. Students in the 12th grade from these schools were chosen using the stratified

proportionate sampling method. After rectification, the final sample of 1,149 students was generated using the data that were originally obtained from 1,300 students. Figure 1 explains the number of pupils by gender that is, male (n = 589) and female (n = 560), parenting style that is, democratic parenting style (DPS) (n = 686), autocratic parenting style (APS) (n = 274), permissive parenting style (PPS) (n = 154), and uninvolved parenting style (UPS) (n = 35), and stream that is, arts (n = 679), commerce (n = 211), and science (n=259).

Figure 1. Number of students based on gender, parenting style and stream

2.3. Tools

2.3.1. Academic buoyancy scale

In the current research, academic buoyancy scale, developed by Martin and Marsh was used [46]. It consisted of four items. The scale was first validated in Indian context. The four items of the academic buoyancy scale range from strongly disagree to strongly agree on a seven-point scale. The reliability of the scale was found to be 0.799 (Cronbach alpha) at 0.01 level of confidence. In CFA all the parameters have been shown acceptable values. The value of chi-square minimum/degrees of freedom (CMIN/DF), root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA), relative fit index (RFI), incremental fit index (IFI), tucker-lewis index (TLI), and comparative fit index (CFI) were found to be 0.94, 0.06, 0.000, 0.99, 1.00, 1.00 and 1.00 respectively.

2.3.2. Seven-fold emotional intelligence scale

There are 63 items on the Sevenfold Emotional Intelligence Scale that range from strongly disagree to strongly agree on a five-point scale. This scale was developed by Kaur [47]. Seven factors made up this scale: self-awareness and self-evaluation, self-regulation and responsibility, self-motivation, self-esteem and confidence, empathy and acceptance of others, interpersonal relationships, and social skills. By using the test-retest approach, the reliability of the seven-fold emotional intelligence scale was proven. With a 0.01 level of confidence, the reliability coefficients between the two sets of scores were established to be 0.91, which is significant.

2.3.3. Parenting style scale

A total of 43 elements on a four-point scale, ranging from always to never (always = 4, often = 3, sometimes = 2, never=1), comprise up the parenting style scale. Gupta and Mehtani created this scale [48]. The scale's items are all of a positive character. DPS, APS, PPS, and UPS were the four subscales that made up this scale. At the 0.01 level of confidence, the coefficient value of 0.911 was significant. The Spearman-Brown Prophecy model was used to determine the split-half reliability. It was discovered to be 0.795, which, at a 0.01 level of confidence, was significant.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results of t-test

The results of the t-test on the basis of gender are summarized in Table 1. The findings of the analysis revealed that for academic buoyancy there was a significant difference on the basis of gender. Similarly, there was a significant difference in male and female students in case of emotional intelligence. Furthermore, for all the parenting styles there was a significant difference on the basis of gender. Female students were found to be more buoyant and have more emotional intelligence than the male students. Similarly, female students were reported democratic and UPS at home, whereas, male students reported

autocratic and PPS at home. Therefore, the null hypothesis that, “there is no significant difference in academic buoyancy, emotional intelligence and parenting styles on the basis of gender” is rejected at 0.05 level of confidence.

Table 1. Results of t-test on the basis of gender

	Variable	N	Mean	St. Deviation	SED	t-value	Df	Sig.
Academic buoyancy	Male	589	19.09	3.89	0.16	-3.037	1147	0.002
	Female	560	19.8	4.08	0.172			
Emotional intelligence	Male	589	216.95	30.46	1.255	-2.268	1147	0.024
	Female	560	221.06	31.01	1.31			
DPS	Male	312	36.77	4.71	0.266	-5.095	684	0.000
	Female	374	38.77	5.42	0.28			
APS	Male	159	36.18	4.50	0.357	2.447	272	0.015
	Female	115	34.86	4.20	0.392			
PPS	Male	95	34.72	4.72	0.484	3.914	153	0.000
	Female	59	31.76	4.36	0.563			
UPS	Male	23	28.95	3.25	0.678	-0.446	33	0.034
	Female	12	29.58	5.05	1.458			

Now, there was a significant difference academic buoyancy, emotional intelligence and APS on the basis of stream. For democratic, permissive and UPS, the F-value in ANOVA was found to be insignificant at 0.05 level of confidence. Therefore, the null hypothesis that “there is no significant difference in democratic, permissive and UPS on the basis of stream” is accepted. The values of mean for academic buoyancy, emotional intelligence and APS are summarized in Table 2. Moreover, from the findings of the study, it was evident that the science students were more academically buoyant and emotionally intelligent than arts and commerce students as shown in Table 3.

Table 2. Summary of multiple comparisons among students on basis of stream

	(I) Stream		Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Academic buoyancy	Science	Commerce	3.27801*	0.34545	0.000
		ARTS	3.60968*	0.27205	0.000
	Commerce	Science	-3.27801*	0.34545	0.000
		ARTS	0.33167	0.2936	0.496
	Arts	Science	-3.60968*	0.27205	0.000
		COMMERCE	-0.33167	0.2936	0.496
Emotional intelligence	Science	Commerce	29.47095*	2.56458	0.000
		ARTS	33.20288*	2.01964	0.000
	Commerce	Science	-29.47095*	2.56458	0.000
		ARTS	3.73193	2.1796	0.201
	Arts	Science	-33.20288*	2.01964	0.000
		COMMERCE	-3.73193	2.1796	0.201
APS	Science	Comm	2.26645*	0.85826	0.024
		ARTS	1.48829	0.71656	0.097
	Commerce	Science	-2.26645*	0.85826	0.024
		ARTS	-0.77816	0.67105	0.478
	Arts	Science	-1.48829	0.71656	0.097
		COMMERCE	0.77816	0.67105	0.478

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level

Table 3. Summary of number of students in a stream, mean values, standard deviation and standard error for academic buoyancy, emotional intelligence and APS

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
Academic buoyancy	Science	259	22.1737	4.07544	0.25324
	Commerce	211	18.8957	3.28902	0.22643
	Arts	679	18.5641	3.71256	0.14248
	Total	1149	19.4386	4.00576	0.11817
Emotional intelligence	Science	259	243.9923	31.47079	1.9555
	Commerce	211	214.5213	24.1281	1.66105
	Arts	679	210.7894	27.11863	1.04072
	Total	1149	218.9591	30.78778	0.90828
APS	Science	48	37.0208	3.60549	0.52041
	Commerce	57	34.7544	4.74071	0.62792
	Arts	169	35.5325	4.45351	0.34258
	Total	274	35.6314	4.42262	0.26718

Further, the science students reported APS a home. Therefore, the null hypothesis that, “there is no significant difference in academic buoyancy, emotional intelligence and APS on the basis of stream” is rejected at 0.05 level of confidence.

3.2. Results of correlation

To test ne next hypothesis, the correlation analysis has been done. The value of Pearson correlation coefficient for different variables is summarized in Tables 4 and 5. There was a positive and strong relationship between academic buoyancy and emotional intelligence is shown in Table 4. So, we can say that, with increase in emotional intelligence academic buoyancy of the individual has been increased.

Table 4. Correlation between academic buoyancy and emotional intelligence

Pearson correlation		
Emotional Intelligence	1	0.641
Academic Buoyancy	0.641	1

Table 5. Correlation between different parenting styles and academic buoyancy and emotional intelligence

	Pearson correlations	
	Emotional intelligence	Academic buoyancy
DPS	0.479**	0.522**
APS	0.412**	0.474**
PPS	-0.357**	-0.622**
UPS	-0.549**	-0.514**

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

In case of parenting styles, democratic and APS were found to be positively related to academic buoyancy and emotional intelligence, this means that, academic buoyancy and emotional intelligence will be increased with democratic and APS. Whereas, permissive and UPS were found to be negatively related to academic buoyancy and emotional intelligence. Figure 2 summarises the values of the coefficient of connection between academic buoyancy, emotional intelligence, and various parenting approaches. Graphical representation clearly indicates the relationship between the variables. The relationships between academic buoyancy, emotional intelligence, and academic buoyancy were explained by these values, both directly and indirectly. So, we can conclude that, academic buoyancy and emotional intelligence will decrease with permissive and uninvolved parenting styles as shown in Table 5. Therefore, the null hypothesis that, “there is no significant relationship between academic buoyancy, emotional intelligence and parenting styles” is rejected at 0.01 level of confidence.

Figure 2. Correlation between parenting styles and academic buoyancy and values of Pearson coefficient significant at 0.01 level of confidence

3.3. Results of regression

The results of regression analysis explained that all the four models are significant at 0.05 level of confidence. In case of model 1, 2 and 3 in Table 6, the dominant predictor of academic buoyancy was parenting style. But in model 4, the value of unstandardized coefficient of UPS was found to be insignificant. It means that, UPS did not contribute in the prediction of academic buoyancy and the dominant predictor of academic buoyancy was found to be emotional intelligence. From the results summarized in Table 6 it is evident that the contribution of emotional intelligence in all the models is positive, which means that academic buoyancy will increase with increase in emotional intelligence. But in model 3, there is negative contribution of PPS which means that, academic buoyancy will decrease with increase in permissive behavior of the parents. The contribution of democratic and APS found to be positive in determining the academic buoyancy. In Table 6, different regression equations are summarized. The value of R and R² explains the goodness of fit of the regression model. The Table 6 also demonstrates the contribution of different parenting styles and emotional intelligence towards academic buoyancy.

Table 6. Summary of results of regression analysis showing the values of R, R², adjusted R², regression equations and dominating predictor

	Independent variables	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Regression equation	Dominant predictor of academic buoyancy
Model 1	EI, DPS	0.726	0.527	0.525	AB = -0.791 + (0.066 × EI) + (0.188 × DPS)	DPS
Model 2	EI, APS	0.788	0.621	0.618	AB = -4.045 + (0.083 × EI) + (0.156 × APS)	APS
Model 3	EI, PPS	0.696	0.484	0.478	AB = 17.792 + (0.03 × EI) + (-0.271 × PPS)	PPS
Model 4	EI, UPS	0.832	0.692	0.673	AB = -2.551 + (0.104 × EI)	EI

3.4. Discussion of results

The literature review revealed that the academic buoyancy was found to be influenced by variables like self-efficacy, grit, stress, anxiety, and psychological risk, but also related to personal best goal and well-being of the students. Few studies were also revealed the relationship between academic buoyancy and parenting styles and buoyancy and emotional intelligence. But academic buoyancy was not studied with emotional intelligence and parenting styles among the students of senior secondary level. So, this gap was identified and studied by the researcher.

The current research explained that, academic buoyancy directly related to emotional intelligence, democratic and APS while negatively correlated to uninvolved and PPS. Moreover, the findings of the research revealed that academic buoyancy of students of science stream is higher than the students of commerce and humanities stream. All the independent factors, including parenting style and emotional intelligence, are predictors of academic buoyancy. If we compare the regression findings, we can see that parenting style is the main indicator of academic buoyancy, whether it has a favorable or negative impact. If we closely examine the regression equations, we find that emotional intelligence is the second factor that has the greatest impact on academic buoyancy after parental style.

The findings of this research revealed that, female students have higher academic buoyancy than male students. This result is in support with the research of Martin and Marsh which revealed the gender difference [49]. The emotional intelligence of female pupils is also higher than that of male students. This conclusion is supported by earlier research, which showed that girls had stronger emotional intelligence than boys [50]. The treatment of female students at home is more democratic than that of male students. Additionally, prior research has demonstrated that parenting practices differ according to a student's gender [51]. The data implies that the boys encounter more APS than girls. Previous research [52] backs up this finding. At home, the parents of the male pupils exhibit greater latitude. Previous study demonstrating the gender difference in PPS is consistent with our findings [53]. Mean score of the male student is lower than female students, which indicates that female students receive uninvolved parenting at home.

The current study explored that parenting style and emotional intelligence were the potent factors which influence academic buoyancy. But further in-depth studies are required to confirm these results. A bigger sample size and different population should be necessary for future study. This study was descriptive rather than experimental. Regarding the mediatory effects of the research factors on the academic buoyancy of senior secondary school students, definitive findings cannot be drawn. Therefore, doing experimental research is feasible and may provide a more realistic representation of students' thought processes.

This study clarified the significance of academic buoyancy for students' academic journeys as well as the impact of emotional intelligence and parenting practices on buoyancy. Therefore, in order to improve the academic buoyancy of senior secondary school students, a variety of interventions and initiatives should be implemented by educational institutions, policymakers, and governmental organisations. The school

administrations and government agencies should host seminars and workshops for parents of students so that parents may modify their parenting approaches and support their child's academic success. We may draw the conclusion that academic buoyancy and emotional intelligence, academic buoyancy and DPS, and academic buoyancy and APS are all positively and significantly correlated. Furthermore, both parenting style and emotional intelligence are predictors of academic buoyancy.

4. CONCLUSION

The current study's findings show that the primary predictor of academic buoyancy is parental style. Therefore, a variety of measures should be created by government agencies and school administrators to inform parents of senior secondary children about this information. The school administration and government entities should provide seminars and workshops for parents of senior secondary students so that parents may modify their parenting practices and improve their child's academic buoyancy. The second most significant factor affecting senior secondary students' academic buoyancy is emotional intelligence. Academic buoyancy and emotional intelligence are positively correlated. Therefore, the principal of the school and the faculty should try to improve the emotional intelligence of the senior secondary pupils. The organization of several seminars for senior secondary pupils will help them develop their emotional intelligence.

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